

The SW Iberian Serie Negra Group (Ossa-Morena Complex, Variscan Orogen): a key element in the dynamic evolution of the peri-Gondwanan arc-related basins

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The Ediacaran Serie Negra Group is an element of the basement of the SW Iberian Massif, where it is included in the recently defined Ossa-Morena Complex (OMC; Díez Fernández & Arenas 2015). The Serie Negra Group is constituted by two different members, from bottom to top, the Montemolín and Tentudía formations. The Montemolín Fm. (c. 600 Ma) is constituted by fine-grained metapelites and, to a lesser extent, by metagreywackes intercalated with metabasites derived from sills and volcanic rocks. The Tentudía Fm. (c. 565–540 Ma) consists of metagreywackes, intercalations of black quartzites, black cherts, and scarce metabasites. On top of the Serie Negra Group, there is a sequence that rests discordant and crosses the Precambrian–Cambrian boundary, the Malcocinado Fm., which consists of andesitic breccias and flows with minor levels of metasedimentary rocks intruded by granitic bodies. Both the Serie Negra Group and the Malcocinado Fm. were deposited in a peri-Gondwanan volcanic arc setting.

Recent studies reveal the complex dynamic of this margin, active at least between c. 750 and c. 500 Ma. This geodynamic scenario includes the opening and closing of oceanic basins induced by cyclical variations in the subduction angle that generate stages of extension and compression at the margin (Arenas et al. 2018, Díez Fernández et al. 2021). The obtained geochemical and Nd-Sr isotopic data of the Serie Negra Group confirm that its two formations were deposited in a sedimentary basin opened close to a volcanic arc at the Gondwana margin, whose supplies came from old (cratonic) sources mixed with juvenile material (Rojo-Pérez et al. 2019). Despite this shared geodynamic context, the geochemical and isotopic characteristics of the two formations comprising the Serie Negra Group reveal some significant differences, possibly caused by their deposition at different stages during the evolution of the active margin. Immobile elements patterns (e.g. Sr, Sc, La/Th, La/Sc) of the Montemolín Fm. are consistent with those expected for sediments deposited in an island arc setting. Moreover, this formation shows high homogeneity and slight variation in its Nd and Sr isotopic sources (TDM= 1747–1892 Ma; Rojo-Pérez et al. 2021). These features are compatible with the significant volume of mafic rocks included in this formation, which was likely generated during immature stages of the arc. However, the same parameters studied in the Tentudía Fm. (TDM= 1686–1918 Ma; Rojo-Pérez et al. 2021) suggest minor recycling and heterogeneous sources, compatible with more mature stages at the active margin.

The identification of the opening of a fore-arc basin in the vicinity of this arc (c. 600 Ma; Arenas et al. 2018) is in agreement with the geochemistry and isotopic sources obtained for the Montemolín Fm. Later compressional stages affecting the margin, such as those related to the so-called Cadomian orogeny (c. 560–540 Ma), lead to a progressive arc dismantling and further erosion. These processes coincide in time with the estimated age of the Tentudía Fm., and are compatible with the geochemical and isotopic features that suggest a greater input of supplies derived from slightly more heterogeneous sources. The deposition of the Serie Negra Group seems to record different evolutionary stages of a sedimentary basin. This basin was located within the same geodynamic setting concerning the evolution of a magmatic arc built on the thinned continental margin of Gondwana. Hence, it can be

concluded that the siliciclastic basin opened in the context of the peri-Gondwanan magmatic arcs, can provide significant information in relation to the dynamic evolution of these regions.

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